

Conference abstract: Synthesised nanoparticles: Pinotage red wine silver nanoparticles (PRW-AgNPs)

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What they were made for: The as synthesised PRW-AgNPs are to be applied as an antibacterial agent in food related settings.

With my work I have successfully performed the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using red wine as a natural reducing and stabilising agent. This then makes this study a sustainable and innovative approach to nanoparticle synthesis. Through optimising the reaction conditions to abide by green chemistry principles, green optimum conditions for the synthesis were obtained and stable PRW-AgNPs with a characteristic surface plasmon resonance peak around 428 nm were produced. The testing of antibacterial activity against foodborne pathogens will provide insight into the potential application of PRW-AgNPs as eco-friendly antibacterial agents. It is well known that antibacterial resistance is a global problem and therefore novel and eco-friendly nanomaterials could be part of the solution. This project not only looks at the benefits of the as synthesised NPs but also assesses their possible toxicity effects, this is commonly ignored especially in South Africa as there are no toxicity profiles and regulations put in place for the use nanomaterials. Testing both antibacterial activity and toxicity ensures that the nanoparticles are not only effective but also safe for use in food-related applications. This research contributes to the growing field of green nanotechnology but also advances understanding of how red wine's bioactive polyphenols can enhance nanoparticle functionality and biocompatibility for food safety applications.